

BASIC CONCEPTS OF GAME THEORY AND TYPES OF EQUILIBRIUM

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the role of game theory in economics, focusing on its application to strategic decision-making, competition, and resource allocation. Game theory, particularly in the context of non-cooperative and cooperative games, offers critical insights into the interactions between individuals and organizations in various economic settings. The theory's evolution, from von Neumann and Morgenstern's foundational work to John Nash's equilibrium concept, has significantly advanced the understanding of economic behavior.

It is known that game theory plays an important role in economics, as it helps to analyze competition, strategy, and decision-making processes. Game theory mainly studies strategic interactions between one or more players (individuals or organizations). This theory is used in solving economic problems, as well as in various fields, such as marketing, politics, and ecology.

The science of game theory and process research is concerned with the creation and implementation of methods for more effective functioning of management organizational systems. The subject of this science is a system of management of several interconnected units. At all stages of the development of society, efforts are made to conduct business on the basis of a well-structured plan. This is especially important in the current conditions when market relations are being restored. In order to determine the direction of effective economic development, it is necessary to master the methods of quantitative modeling of processes. This is necessary for the development of short-term and strategic plans within the national economy, taking into account large-scale and long-term events, and identifying various options for economic development. Also, for creating a program for regional development, providing coordinated plans for research and development, for performing some complex work in targeted program planning, for allocating resources, and for ensuring the rational functioning of the enterprise in the external market environment. In many cases, the science of process research, which is a direction of applied mathematics that has been developing rapidly and effectively in recent times, can serve as a basis for studying organizational issues.

Institutional economics uses game theory, based on the ideas in John von Neumann and Oscar Morgenstern's book "Game Theory and Economic Behavior" (1944), to build formal models [47]. The development of this theory is associated with the concept of equilibrium, introduced by John Nash in 1950. This developed a method for solving non-cooperative (non-coalition) games. By 1994, three researchers were awarded the Nobel Prize in Economics for the first analysis of equilibrium in the theory of "non-cooperative games". These were: Reinhard Selten

(Germany), Jozef Nash (USA), John S. Harsany (Hungarian origin - USA). Among the main features of this research method, the following should be distinguished: First, game theory deals with the analysis of situations in which individuals act in concert: the solution of each condition affects the outcome of their interaction and, in turn, the decisions of other individuals. When solving the problem of their actions, an individual must put themselves in the place of the counterparties. To build formal models of institutional economics, game theory is used, based on the ideas in the book "Game Theory and Economic Behavior" (1944) by John von Neumann and Oscar Morgenstern [47]. The development of this theory is associated with the concept of equilibrium situations introduced by John Nash in 1950. This led to the development of a method for solving non-cooperative games. By 1994, three researchers were awarded the Nobel Prize in Economics for the first analysis of equilibrium in the theory of "non-cooperative games". These are: Reinhard Selten (Germany), Jozef Nash (USA), John S. Harsany (Hungarian origin - USA). Among the main features of this research method, the following should be distinguished. First, game theory deals with the analysis of situations of mutually conditioned actions of individuals: the solution of each condition affects the outcome of interaction and, in turn, the decisions of other individuals. When solving the problem of his actions, the individual must put himself in the place of the counterparties.

Cooperative (coalition) games are situations in which information exchange and alliance formation are possible between participants. In non-cooperative (non-coalition) games, a single participant is the starting point for analysis, in which information exchange and alliance formation between participants are not possible. Games are mainly represented in the form of a matrix. In non-cooperative (non-coalition) games, participants interact in a conflicting manner. Each participant seeks to increase his own gain. The gain of one leads to the defeat of the other. The action plan of each participant in the game to resolve conflict situations is called the strategy of the game participant.

For each interaction, there may be different types of equilibria: dominant strategy equilibrium, Nash equilibrium, Stackelberg equilibrium, and Pareto equilibrium.

A dominant strategy equilibrium is a plan of action that provides the participant with the highest utility regardless of the actions of the other participant.

Nash equilibrium is a situation in which none of the players can unilaterally increase their payoff by changing their plan of action.

Stackelberg equilibrium is a situation in which none of the players can unilaterally increase their payoff. In this case, the decision is first made by the first player, and then it becomes known to the second player.

Pareto equilibrium is a situation in which the state of one of the players cannot be improved without worsening the state of the second player.

In conclusion, in the study of game theory and processes, optimal solutions to many current problems, including those in the field of economics, are solved using the minmax method. Methods and algorithms for obtaining maximum profit are developed, in which the number of products delivered to consumers and the profit are systematically planned.

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